

Supplementary document of the article titled 'Quality Evaluation Meta-model for Open Source Software'

It should be noted that this document is an extension of the article named "A **Quality Evaluation Meta-model for Open Source Software**." This document is referenced in the article, and this article will be referred to as the "main document" in the following sentences. In this document, as mentioned in the main document, the practical application of the OSS-QMM will be demonstrated over two existing OSS quality models, namely OpenBRR [14] and OSMM [13] (*References are given in the main document*). These two existing quality models were derived from our OSS-QMM and applied in practice with two case studies (CS). The results obtained in this document will be compared with the results of Case study-1 obtained in the main document, and all results will be discussed in Section 5 of the main document.

Performing the Case study-2 (OpenBRR) and Case study-3 (OSMM)

As shown in Fig. 3 in the main document, the terms of the OSS-QMM are classified as specification, measurement, and evaluation. In the *specification* part, the required preparations have been performed before applying CS-2 and CS-3. Before the application of case studies is demonstrated, the following issues should be specified;

- As in CS 1, the same open-source ERP systems will be evaluated in terms of maintainability in these two case studies as specified main document
- Unlike CS 1, different sub-characteristics will be used since the OpenBRR and OSMM has their own sub-characteristics of maintainability, as shown in Appendix-A and Appendix-B, respectively.
- Unlike CS 1, different measures and measurable concepts will be used since the OpenBRR and OSMM has their own measure and measurable concepts, as shown in Appendix-A and Appendix-B, respectively.
- As in CS 1, the same methods/techniques/functions were used in these two case studies, as mentioned in Table 5 in the main document.
- As in CS 1, the same viewpoint (i.e., developer-11 Expert) will be used to carry out CS 2 and CS 3.
- Unlike CS 1, since these two quality models consist of only measurable concepts related to the community-based aspect, the weight of the OSS aspect will not be used in these two case studies.

Apart from those mentioned above, unlike CS 1, the different weights for sub-characteristics will be used since these two quality models consist of their sub-characteristic of maintainability, as shown in Appendix-A and Appendix-B, respectively. In this context, the AHP process is employed to assign weight to these sub-characteristics of OpenBRR and OSMM separately, as detailed is given Section 4.1.5.2 in the main document (see for detail [84-86]). For this purpose, semi-structured interviews are held with 11 experts to perform pair-wise comparisons among these sub-characteristics in the scope of the AHP process, as detailed is explained in Section 4.1.5.2 (Table 8) of the main document. As a result of this process, the priority weight is obtained according to the judgment of each expert for OpenBRR and OSMM, as shown in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively. Then, these weights from all experts for each sub-characteristic were averaged, and final weights were obtained for each sub-characteristic, as shown in these tables.

Table 1. The weights for each sub-characteristics according to the expert's judgements, the average of these weights, and the CR values for OpenBRR

Sub-char. /Expert	E1	E2	E3	E4	E5	E6	E7	E8	E9	E10	E11	Avg.
Quality	0.4596	0.5542	0.5423	0.3498	0.2391	0.3577	0.5194	0.1864	0.273	0.227	0.204	0.3558
Support	0.1572	0.1573	0.1624	0.1584	0.4327	0.3785	0.1213	0.2281	0.3233	0.1139	0.3410	0.2340
Document	0.0886	0.0810	0.0656	0.0825	0.0889	0.0848	0.0730	0.0836	0.1049	0.3845	0.0904	0.1116
Community	0.2944	0.2074	0.2295	0.4091	0.2391	0.1788	0.2862	0.5017	0.298	0.2734	0.3638	0.2983
CR	0.0169	0.0441	0.0532	0.0051	0.0074	0.0023	0.0500	0.0076	0.0170	0.0223	0.0170	0.0220

Table 2. The weights for each sub-characteristics according to the expert's judgements, the average of these weights, and the CR values for OSMM

Sub-char. /Expert	E1	E2	E3	E4	E5	E6	E7	E8	E9	E10	E11	Avg.
Product Property	0.4717	0.3499	0.5139	0.3712	0.4253	0.2643	0.2223	0.5894	0.2498	0.4129	0.2734	0.3767
Use	0.1931	0.1796	0.1569	0.1843	0.2305	0.1905	0.4169	0.1710	0.1470	0.2439	0.2279	0.2129
Acceptance	0.0969	0.0809	0.0794	0.0898	0.1492	0.0755	0.1105	0.0836	0.0732	0.0991	0.1139	0.0956
Integration	0.2381	0.3894	0.2496	0.3545	0.1948	0.4695	0.2501	0.1558	0.5297	0.2439	0.3845	0.3145
CR	0.0152	0.0231	0.0655	0.0383	0.0170	0.0440	0.0170	0.0393	0.0327	0.0225	0.0223	0.0306

Since these two quality models consist of only measurable concepts related to the community-based aspect, the weight of the OSS aspect will not be used in these two case studies. Therefore, the concept of the *weighting aggregation method* (Fig. 1 in the main document) is not employed. Accordingly, the weights given in Table 1 and Table 2 is the final weight for each sub-characteristic.

In the *measurement* part, the measure of these two quality models is quantified. The list of measurable concepts and related measures is given in Appendix-A and Appendix-B for OpenBRR and OSMM, respectively. A detailed definition of each measure is given in the document of these quality models [13][14]. All these measures are *base measures* that can be quantified directly. As specified in our OSS-QMM, a *measurement method* is determined to compute these measures, and these measures were computed *manually* by obtaining them from databases of these open-source ERP systems. The AHP method has been implemented in the specification part, but now the TOPSIS method will be employed using the outputs of the AHP process. The steps of TOPSIS are represented in Fig. 5 of the main document, and also its equation is given in Table 6 of the main document (see for detail [86-88]). As in CS 1, the TOPSIS process is performed. In this context, the Table 3A-E is obtained for OpenBRR, and Table 4A-E is obtained for OSMM as follows:

Table 3. List of the tables for CS-2 (OpenBRR): (A) Final weights of sub-characteristics, impacts, measurable concepts (MC), the measure associated with MC, values of measures, and decision matrix B, (B) Normalized decision matrix R, (C) Weighted normalized decision matrix V, (D) Value of Positive Ideal Solution and Negative Ideal Solution, and (E) Separation measurement (S+ and S-), final quality evaluation score, and rank values

(A)

OSS aspect	Community-based aspect											
Sub-charac.	Quality						Support		Documentation		Community	
Final weight	0.3558						0.234		0.1116		0.2983	
Impact	+		-		+		+		+		+	
M. concept	MC1		MC2		MC3		MC4		MC5		MC6	
Measure	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M7	M11
Adempiere	3	3	279	32	54	26	248	5	4	5	248	12
Compiere	2	2	251	30	88	24	192	5	4	5	192	13
Apacahc Ofbiz	4	3	185	28	63	19	284	3	5	5	284	15

(B)

M. concept	MC1		MC2		MC3		MC4		MC5		MC6	
Measure	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M7	M11
Adempiere	0.5570	0.6396	0.6668	0.6149	0.4464	0.6473	0.5861	0.6509	0.5298	0.5773	0.5861	0.5173
Compiere	0.3713	0.4264	0.5998	0.5764	0.7275	0.5975	0.4537	0.6509	0.5298	0.5773	0.4537	0.5604
Apacahc Ofbiz	0.7427	0.6396	0.4421	0.5380	0.5208	0.4730	0.6712	0.3905	0.6622	0.5773	0.6712	0.6466

(C)

M. concept	MC1	MC2	MC3	MC4	MC5	MC6	MC7	MC8	MC9	MC9
Measure	Avg. (M1,M2)	Avg. (M3, M4)	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M7	M11
Adempiere	0.2129	0.2280	0.2280	0.2303	0.1372	0.1523	0.0591	0.0644	0.1748	0.1543
Compiere	0.1419	0.2093	0.2093	0.2126	0.1062	0.1523	0.0591	0.0644	0.1354	0.1672
Apacahe Ofbiz	0.2459	0.1744	0.1744	0.1683	0.1571	0.0914	0.0739	0.0644	0.2002	0.1929

(D)

A+ (PIS)	0.2459	0.1744	0.2280	0.1683	0.1571	0.1523	0.0739	0.0644	0.2002	0.1929
A- (NIS)	0.1419	0.2280	0.1744	0.2303	0.1062	0.0914	0.0591	0.0644	0.1354	0.1543

(E)

	S+	S-	Score	Rank
Adempiere	0.1027	0.1189	0.5364	2
Compiere	0.1484	0.0759	0.3383	3
A. Ofbiz	0.0811	0.1613	0.6653	1

Table 4. List of the tables for CS-3 (OSMM): (A) Final weights of sub-characteristics, impacts, measurable concepts (MC), the measure associated with MC, values of measures, and decision matrix B, **(B)** Normalized decision matrix R, **(C)** Weighted normalized decision matrix V, **(D)** Value of Positive Ideal Solution and Negative Ideal Solution, and **(E)** Separation measurement (S+ and S-), final quality evaluation score, and rank values

(A)

OSS aspect	Community-based aspect								
	Product				Integration		Use		Acceptance
Sub-charac.	0.3767				0.3145		0.0956		0.2129
Final weight	0.3767				0.3145		0.0956		0.2129
Impact	+	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	+
M. concept	MC1	MC2	MC3	MC4	MC5	MC6	MC7	MC8	MC9
Measure	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9
Adempiere	5	3	5	5	5	5	5	3	1
Compiere	5	3	5	3	3	5	5	3	1
Apacahe Ofbiz	5	5	3	5	5	3	3	5	3

(B)

M. concept	MC1	MC2	MC3	MC4	MC5	MC6	MC7	MC8	MC9
Measure	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9
Adempiere	0.5774	0.4575	0.6509	0.6509	0.6509	0.6509	0.6509	0.4575	0.3015
Compiere	0.5774	0.4575	0.6509	0.3906	0.3906	0.6509	0.6509	0.4575	0.3015
Apacahe Ofbiz	0.5774	0.7625	0.3906	0.6509	0.6509	0.3906	0.3906	0.7625	0.9045

(C)

M. concept	MC1	MC2	MC3	MC4	MC5	MC6	MC7	MC8	MC9
Measure	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9
Adempiere	0.2175	0.1723	0.2452	0.2452	0.2047	0.2047	0.0622	0.0437	0.0642
Compiere	0.2175	0.1723	0.2452	0.1471	0.1228	0.2047	0.0622	0.0437	0.0642
Apacahe Ofbiz	0.2175	0.2872	0.1471	0.2452	0.2047	0.1228	0.0373	0.0729	0.1926

(D)

A+ (PIS)	0.2175	0.2872	0.2452	0.2452	0.2047	0.2047	0.0622	0.0729	0.1926
A- (NIS)	0.2175	0.1723	0.1471	0.1471	0.1228	0.1228	0.0373	0.0437	0.0642

(E)

	S+	S-	Score	Rank
Adempiere	0.1747	0.1824	0.5107	2
Compiere	0.2164	0.1301	0.3755	3
A. Ofbiz	0.1301	0.2164	0.6244	1

In the *evaluation* part, the same process is performed as in CS 1. Since this process is explained in detail in Section 4.1.6 of the main document, it is not repeated here. That is, the final quality score obtained for each ERP system was interpreted by the concept of *evaluation function* separately for these two case studies. In this context, in these two case studies, as shown in Fig. 1A and Fig.1B, the linear utility function was used as the concept of the evaluation function to interpret the final quality scores. As can be seen from the figures, x_{max} will be 1, and therefore, according to the formula $u = x/x_{max}$ the $u(x)$ value of each ERP system will be the same as the final quality score of them. After all these processes, the evaluation results can be produced for CS-2 and CS-3 with the concept of the *evaluation result*.

Figure 1. Linear utility function according to the final quality score of each OSS products in (A) OpenBRR, (B) OSMM

As can be seen from Fig. 1A and Fig. 1B, the preferable product Apache Ofbiz was determined in terms of maintainability, and it was followed by Adempiere and Compiere, respectively. Also, considering that $a > b$ in the figure, it can be easily seen that the difference in quality between Compiere and Adempiere is greater than the difference in quality between Adempiere and Apache Ofbiz.

Appendix-A: sub-characteristic, measurable concepts, and measure of OpenBRR

Sub-char.	Measurable Concept	Measure
Quality	MC1: Productivity of contributors	M1: Number of minor releases in past 12 months
		M2: Number of point/patch releases in past 12 months
	MC2: Fault proneness of contributor	M3: Number of open bugs for the last 6 months
		M4: Number of P1/critical bugs opened
MC3: Performance of contributor	M5: Number of bugs fixed in last 6 months (compared to # of bugs opened)	
MC4: Time management failure of contributor (reluctance of contributor)	M6: Average bug age for P1 in last 6 months	
Support	MC5: The activeness of the community	M7: Average volume of general mailing list in the last 6 months
	MC6: Quality of professional support	M8: Types of supports provided
Documentation	MC7: Completeness of documentation	M9: Existence of various kinds of documentation
	MC8: Documentation of user contribution	M10: User contribution framework
Community	MC5: The activeness of the community	M7: Average volume of general mailing list in the last 6 months
	MC9: Size of contributor	M11: Number of unique code contributors in the last 6 months

Appendix-B: sub-characteristic, measurable concepts, and measure of OSMM

Sub-char.	Measurable concept	Measure
Product	MC1: Maturity of project	M1: Product age
	MC2: Degree of allowing modification	M2: License type
	MC3: Diversity of lead developer	M3: Human hierarchies
	MC4: The difficulty of being a core developer	M4: Developer community
Integration	MC5: The complexity of the design	M5: Modularity
	MC6: The degree of product interaction	M6: Collaboration with other products
Use	MC7: The degree of support	M7: Support
	MC8: Ease of deployment	M8: Product Deployment
Acceptance	MC9: The activeness of the user	M9: User Community